

Does the presence of only specific active sites control the switch of selectivity from C₁ to C₂₊ products in CO₂RR?

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ABSTRACT

There is an extensive but not conclusive debate about the factors determining selectivity in the competitive path to C₁ vs. C₂₊ products in the electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ (CO₂RR). While the predominant indication is that C₂₊ products require specific active sites and/or surface features of the electrocatalyst, we prove here that selectivity can be entirely switched from C₂₊ to C₁ products by controlling H⁺ accessibility. This indicates that the electrocatalytic path is determined by proton availability rather than the intrinsic presence of specific active sites. To validate this, we investigated CO₂RR on CuO nanoplates with identical structural and morphological features (confirmed by XRD, SEM-EDX, TEM, HRTEM analyses) but varying wettability characteristics using different precursors (Li or Na), thereby modulating the surface H⁺ accessibility. The applied potential also controls this accessibility. By analysing Faradaic selectivity as a function of applied potential across CuO nanoplate samples with different wettability, we observe a transition from 100 % C₂₊ selectivity to 100 % C₁ selectivity, with the potential threshold for this switch dependent on wettability. Our findings demonstrate that the C₂₊ vs. C₁ product pathway in CO₂RR is not an intrinsic property of the electrocatalyst but is governed by the availability of surface protons, which is a function of the operating conditions and electrode/electrocatalyst characteristics that regulate proton access to the catalyst surface.

1. Introduction

The electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ (CO₂RR) is a promising solution that converts carbon dioxide into valuable chemicals and fuels, presenting a potential pathway towards a circular carbon economy [1, 2]. The choice of catalytic materials is of critical importance in determining efficiency and product selectivity in CO₂RR. Copper-based materials, in particular, have garnered significant attention due to their unique ability to facilitate the formation of valuable hydrocarbons and oxygenates, such as ethanol and ethylene [3,4]. Unlike other catalysts, which typically produce formic acid or carbon monoxide, Cu-based nanomaterials exhibit a distinct capability to catalyse the formation of multi-carbon products (C₂₊), making them prime candidates for advancing CO₂RR technologies [5]. However, achieving high selectivity and yield to form C₂₊ products remains challenging due to the involvement of multiple electron transfer and the competing side

reaction, i.e., the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) [6,7].

The CO₂RR mechanism to C₂₊ products on Cu-based catalysts involves multiple steps, with *CO (i.e., chemisorbed CO on the surface) being typically indicated as the critical intermediate. The initial step is the reduction of CO₂ to the *CO intermediate, which undergoes further reductions to species such as *CHO, *COH, *COCO, *OCCHO, or *OCCOH. These intermediates have different binding strengths on the catalyst surface, which ultimately determines the distribution of final products [8]. The dimerization of *CO is often considered the rate-determining step in the process. High coverage and strong binding of *CO on the catalyst surface are essential for promoting the C–C coupling and forming C₂₊ products such as ethylene, ethanol, or acetate [9]. Two vicinal active sites are commonly believed to be required for C–C coupling. The reaction pathway of CO₂RR, according to the literature, is thus primarily dependent on the presence of specific active sites in the electrocatalyst, determining the C–C coupling step [3,10–14].

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Several authors have also highlighted the role of microenvironment, confinement effects and local pH [15–17]. Nevertheless, the design criteria and modelling approaches are typically based on the identification of the intrinsic features of the electrocatalyst surface, such as the presence of sub-surface oxides or defective sites, Cu⁺ species and grain boundaries, Cu facets, nano-morphology, etc. [18–20], which make possible the formation of the vicinal sites necessary for C-C coupling. In contrast, the path of hydrogenation of this intermediate deriving from C-C coupling depends on the local characteristics, such as the micro-environment. Thus, the C₁ vs C₂₊ selectivity is typically an intrinsic electrocatalyst property, while the product selectivity (for example, to ethylene vs. ethanol) depends on other electrocatalyst properties.

Summarising in a nutshell the extensive mechanistic studies on multicarbon product formation during CO₂RR [3,13,14,21,22], the formation of intermediate species such as OCCO, determining the formation of C₂₊ products, is an intrinsic property of the electrocatalysts, which depends on aspects such as the metal type, crystalline faces, presence of multiple valence states, etc. The microenvironment, including aspects such as wettability, plays a secondary role by influencing the population of ad-species or intermediates, thereby affecting the nature of the final products.

Generally, the active phase for CO₂RR is associated with metallic copper nanoparticles (NPs), regardless of the catalyst's initial oxidation state [23,24]. These NPs can eventually be tuned by preparing Cu-based bimetallic tandem catalysts [25,26]. For example, a dendritic-type nano-morphology could be induced by the modification of Cu NPs with Fe [27], enhancing the selectivity to higher carbon-chain liquid products (i.e. ethanol, isopropanol, acetic acid). The concept of the density of undercoordinated Cu sites during CO₂RR was also recently highlighted by electrochemical atomic force microscopy (EC-AFM) studies [28]. The nanomorphology and associated aspects, such as the presence of nanocavities creating a local micro environment, are thus associated with precise control of the synthesis procedures.

A further crucial question is whether the mechanistic assumptions are also valid in passing from simple to more realistic electrocatalytic reactor operations, e.g. operating at the high current densities required for practical relevance, typically involving gas-diffusion electrodes and zero-gap type electrocatalytic cells [29]. If the mechanism controlling the C₁ vs. C₂₊ products were an intrinsic feature of the electrocatalyst, a minor dependence should be observed on the type of reactor/cell. However, experimental evidence suggests otherwise [30].

We thereby designed a series of experiments to address the aforementioned questions using the same catalytic material, i.e. CuO. We selected CuO nanoplates synthesised via the hydrothermal route due to their demonstrated effectiveness in converting CO₂ to C₂₊ products (e.g., ethylene) [31]. In addition, these materials can form Cu(I)/Cu(0) interfaces, which have recently been indicated as crucial for producing C₂₊ products (like ethanol) in CO₂RR [32]. We prepared CuO nanoplates with similar structural characteristics and nanomorphology, differing only in the precursor used during the synthesis (Li or Na) to induce distinct wettability properties. This approach enabled the preparation of a homogeneous set of electrodes with identical nanostructure but different surface wettability, allowing the systematic study of the impact of H⁺ accessibility to the surface sites on CO₂RR performance [33,34].

The electrocatalytic materials were thoroughly characterized to define their morphological and structural properties, with the aim of confirming that the CuO nanoplates used as catalysts were nearly identical, differing only in their wettability properties, which were modulated by varying the precursor during synthesis. For comparison, a third type of CuO sample, characterized by a different nanomorphology (i.e., aggregates of round nanoparticles), was also prepared as a reference material. However, the scope is neither to study the behaviour of CuO nanoplates by correlating their reactivity to structural features, nor to investigate the role of wettability. These aspects are only functional to have a series of homogeneous electrocatalysts allowing the correlation between the switch from C₁ to C₂₊ paths and proton accessibility to the

surface, which depends on both the applied potential and the wettability characteristics of the electrocatalyst.

A hydrophobic surface limits the accessibility of protons to the electrode surface, thereby influencing the reaction path. Protons are needed in CO₂RR, but enhanced H⁺ diffusion favours their reduction to form H₂ (HER), decreasing Faradaic efficiency (FE) in CO₂RR. Furthermore, we compared the electrocatalytic behaviour of these CuO nanoplates with CuO nanoparticles, which were synthesised using a similar hydrothermal route but exhibited a distinct nanostructure. Although the concept of wettability has been discussed in the literature in reference to CO₂RR [35–37], we will use it here from a different perspective, i.e. as a way to control the surface accessibility of hydrogen species. We observed that increasing the applied voltage can switch the selectivity from C₂₊ to C₁ products, with the voltage threshold for this transition depending on surface H⁺ accessibility.

To obtain reliable indications on the mechanism at relevant conditions, we used gas-diffusion electrodes (GDEs) to increase the local concentration of CO₂ at the electrocatalyst surface [29]. A GDE typically comprises a catalyst layer applied onto a conductive, partially hydrophobic substrate known as the gas-diffusion layer (GDL) [38]. This configuration establishes a three-phase interface, where the gaseous reactants like CO₂ interact with the liquid-phase species (protons, ions) and the solid electrocatalyst, boosting the mass transfer and ensuring a high local concentration of CO₂ directly at the reaction zone [37,39,40]. In addition, we used an optimised flow-type electrochemical device designed to minimise energy losses due to overpotential [29,41].

2. Methods and materials

2.1. Synthesis of the Cu_xO nanoplates

Two CuO electrocatalysts were synthesised via the same hydrothermal treatment in an autoclave to achieve a high electro-active surface area, by adapting the procedure from [42]. To induce differences in wettability properties, a different precursor (i.e., LiOH or NaOH) was added into the autoclave, indicated as CuO (A) and CuO (B), respectively. A third sample, referred to as CuO (R), was also prepared and used as a reference, by calcination of a Cu₂O precursor synthesised using ethylene glycol. The detailed synthesis procedures are as follows:

CuO (A): A solution of 0.58 g of CuCl₂·2H₂O and 0.43 g of LiOH was prepared in 69 mL of distilled water under stirring for 10 min. The solution was transferred to an autoclave and heated in an oven at 180°C for 2 h, with a ramp of 5°C min⁻¹. After cooling to room temperature, the product was recovered by centrifugation and washed three times with ethanol and water to completely remove Li. The final sample was dried in a vacuum oven at 70°C.

CuO (B): This sample was synthesised by dissolving 0.340 g of CuCl₂·2H₂O in 20 mL of distilled water under stirring for 15 min. Next, 20 mL of NaOH was added dropwise, and the mixture was transferred to an autoclave. The autoclave was heated in an oven at 180°C for 2 h, with a ramp of 5°C min⁻¹. After cooling to room temperature, the precipitate was separated by centrifugation and washed three times with ethanol and water to completely remove Na. The sample was then dried in a vacuum oven at 70°C.

CuO (R): The Cu₂O precursor was first synthesised by dissolving 3.3 g of Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O in 69 mL of ethylene glycol under stirring. The mixture was transferred to an autoclave and heated in an oven at 140°C for 1 h, with a heating ramp of 5°C min⁻¹. The resulting Cu₂O sample was separated by centrifugation, washed with water, and dried under vacuum at 80°C. The final CuO sample was obtained by calcining Cu₂O at 450°C for 1 h, with a ramp of 10°C min⁻¹.

2.1.1. Electrode preparation

The CuO electrocatalysts were deposited onto a gas-diffusion layer (GDL, Sigracet 36BB) through a spray drying technique. A weighed amount of the catalyst was mixed with 50 µL of a 10 wt% perfluorinated

Nafion™ solution and 9 mL of 2-propanol, and the mixture was stirred until the formation of a homogeneous suspension. This ink was then sprayed using an airbrush onto the pre-heated GDL, facilitating solvent evaporation and catalyst adhesion to the carbon-based material. All electrodes were prepared with a catalyst loading of 0.5 mg cm⁻² and a geometrical surface area of 5.3 cm².

2.1.2. Characterisation of the electrocatalysts/electrodes

Various physico- and electro-chemical methods have been applied to characterise the samples and determine their properties.

Morphological and structural characterisation. The morphology of the Cu_xO-GDL electrodes was analysed using a Phenom ProX Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), which was equipped with an Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) detector. X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were carried out with a D2 Phaser Bruker diffractometer featuring a CuK α radiation source with a Ni β -filter, operating at 30 kV and 10 mA, to determine the phase composition and crystalline structure. Data were collected across a 2 θ range of 10° to 90°, with a scanning rate of 0.025° s⁻¹. The diffraction peaks were identified by referencing the JCPDS database.

High-Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HR-TEM) images were obtained using a cold field transmission electron microscope (JEM-F200, Jeol, Japan) at an operating voltage of 200 kV. Samples were deposited on 300 mesh Cu TEM grids with holey carbon films.

Electrochemical characterisation. The Cu_xO-GDL electrodes were analysed using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) to assess the internal resistances of the electrochemical system. Measurements were conducted over a frequency range of 1 × 10⁵ to 0.1 Hz, with an amplitude of 0.01 V_{rms}, at different working potentials under a CO₂ stream. The experimental data were fitted to a Randle-like equivalent circuit, consisting of i) a solution resistance (R_s), which accounts for the resistance of the electrolyte and the distance between the working and reference electrodes; ii) a charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), representing the resistance to electron transfer from the electrolyte to the catalyst surface; and iii) a constant phase element (CPE), a theoretical parameter that reflects both resistive and capacitive behaviour.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) profiles were recorded under the same conditions as the CO₂RR tests, conducted under a CO₂ stream, as detailed in the following section. The CV measurements began from the open circuit potential (OCP) and were conducted within the potential range from -1.2 V to 0.2 V versus the Reversible Hydrogen Electrode (RHE).

2.1.3. CO₂RR electrocatalytic tests

A custom-made flow electrocatalytic cell was used for the experiments [41]. The cell, made of Plexiglas (transparent material), has three compartments: an anode, a cathode, and a gas chamber. The anode and cathode sections are separated by a proton-exchange membrane, with different electrolytes flowing through each compartment and continuously recirculated using a peristaltic pump. The membrane is Nafion™ N324, a perfluorosulfonic acid (PFSA) cation-exchange membrane that combines outstanding chemical resistance with the mechanical strength of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE). The gas chamber is adjacent to the cathode chamber, where CO₂ is continuously supplied. It passes through the gas-diffusion layer (GDL) to reach the electrocatalyst deposited on the inner side of the gas-diffusion electrode (GDE). This configuration effectively separates the liquid and gas flows. Gaseous products are continuously collected for analysis from the outlet of the gas chamber, while liquid products accumulate in the catholyte, where they are subsequently analysed. The catholyte consisted of 0.1 M KHCO₃ (saturated with CO₂, resulting in a final pH of 6.8), while the anolyte was 0.1 M KOH. Ultra-pure CO₂ was supplied at a flow rate of 20 mL min⁻¹ to both the cathode reservoir and the gas chamber.

The CO₂RR tests were conducted using a three-electrode configuration. A NiO catalyst, prepared by hydrothermal synthesis [43], was deposited on the GDL (catalyst loading of 0.5 mg cm⁻²) and used as the

counter-electrode for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER). The use of NiO, instead of the more commonly used Pt, significantly reduced the overpotential on the anode side. An Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode (supplied by AMEL) was placed in close proximity to the working electrode to minimise series resistance and error. The measured potentials were then converted to the RHE scale using the following equation:

$$E_{(\text{RHE})} = E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} + 0.059\text{pH} + 0.21 \quad (1)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural and morphological characterisations

The main X-ray diffraction (XRD) peaks for the CuO electrocatalysts are shown in Fig. 1a. These correspond to the (110), ($\bar{1}11$), (111), ($\bar{1}12$), ($\bar{2}02$), (020), (202), ($\bar{1}13$), ($\bar{3}11$), (113), ($\bar{2}20$), and (311) crystallographic planes of CuO, observed at 32.8°, 35.7°, 39.0°, 46.5°, 48.9°, 53.6°, 58.6°, 61.7°, 66.6°, 68.2°, 72.7°, and 75.2° 2 θ , respectively (monoclinic CuO; JCPDS card no. 41-0254). All peaks, except for those corresponding to CuO (R), are sharp, indicating a well-crystallised CuO phase. No diffraction lines corresponding to other phases were detected, nor were any broad reflections indicative of an amorphous phase.

Although the peak intensities align with those expected for monoclinic CuO crystals, a slight variation in the relative intensities of the two most prominent peaks at 35.7° and 39.0°, corresponding to the (002)/($\bar{1}11$) and (111)/(200) planes, respectively, was observed. This change is consistent with a transition to a nanosheet structure when moving from CuO (R) to CuO (A) [44].

The Rietveld refinement was carried out to gain deeper insights into the structural properties of the CuO samples, using the GSAS-II software and analysing the XRD patterns collected over a 2 θ range of 10°–90°, with a step size of 0.04°. A monoclinic CuO structure (space group C 1 2/ c 1) was used as the structural model for the three samples. The refinement procedure involved adjusting parameters such as the scale factor, background, instrumental parameters, unit cell parameters, atomic positions, occupancy factors, and thermal displacement parameters. A Pseudo-Voigt function was employed to model the peak profiles, and refinements were performed by minimising the difference between experimental and calculated patterns via the least squares method. The refinement results (reported in Fig. 1b and Table S1 in Supporting Information -SI) revealed that CuO (A) and CuO (B) have nearly identical crystallographic parameters. By contrast, CuO (R) shows a slightly lower value for the β angle, which results in a larger unit cell volume compared to the other two samples (see Figure S1 and Table S1 in SI).

This observation is further supported by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images (Fig. 2), which clearly show the changes in nanomorphology. For the CuO (B) and especially the CuO (A) electrocatalysts, the presence of distinct nanoplates is evident. In CuO (B), the nanoplates have an average aggregate length ranging from 1 to 3 μm , while in CuO (A), the length increases to between 3.1 and 4.3 μm . In contrast, the CuO (R) sample exhibits aggregates of spherical particles with diameters ranging from 0.30 to 1.5 μm .

Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis confirmed that only CuO crystals were present. There was no contamination from alkaline metals or anions originating from the starting copper salt (see Table S2 in SI). The crystallite size was calculated using Scherrer's equation:

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta\cos\theta} \quad (2)$$

where K is the shape factor (ranging from 0.95 to 0.98), λ is the X-ray wavelength (0.154 nm), β is the width at half maximum of the diffraction peak, and θ is the diffraction angle.

The results indicate that the crystallite size for CuO (A) is 27.7 nm, compared to 18 nm for CuO (B) and 10.1 nm for CuO (R). These findings

Fig. 1. a) X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis for fresh CuO electrocatalysts; b) Rietveld refinement analysis of XRD data for CuO (A) and CuO (B) samples.

Fig. 2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images for a) CuO (A); b) CuO (B) and c) CuO (R).

are consistent with the previous observations of nanostructure morphology. No significant changes were observed in the samples after the catalytic tests.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis was also performed for all three types of samples (CuO (A), CuO (B) and CuO (R)) to gain further insights into their morphology. The TEM image of CuO (A) sample confirms the nanoplate morphology already observed by SEM analysis, with plate width ranging from 130 to 350 nm (Fig. 3a). A similar morphology was observed for the CuO (B) sample, with nanoplates ranging from 150 to 320 nm (Fig. 3b). In contrast, the CuO (R) reference sample shows a markedly different morphology, consisting of aggregates of small round nanoparticles with sizes between 17 and 35 nm ((Figure S2 in SI). HR-TEM measurements (insets in Fig. 3) revealed a lattice fringe spacing of 1.9 Å, corresponding to the (202) plane of the monoclinic CuO structure in both CuO (A) and CuO (B) samples [45].

These TEM/HR-TEM results confirm that the CuO (A) and CuO (B) samples share comparable structural features. Thus, the switch in CO₂RR selectivity from C₁ to C₂₊ products, observed at different potentials for the two samples, cannot be attributed to differences in morphological characteristics. This is a central finding of our study.

While most literature correlates the formation of C₂₊ products in CO₂RR to specific structural properties and active sites, our results suggest that tuning proton accessibility (e.g., by simply changing the precursor choice) can play a decisive role in controlling product selectivity.

3.2. Electrochemical characterisation

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was employed to assess the resistance parameters of the different electrocatalysts and their respective abilities to transfer electrical charge (Fig. 4 and Table S3 in SI).

For all samples, measurements were conducted over a potential range from -0.2 V to -1.0 V vs. RHE. Prior to each EIS measurement, cyclic voltammetry was performed to stabilise the system and ensure that it reached a steady-state condition.

Fig. 5a shows the trend of the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) as a function of the applied potential for the different materials. While the R_{ct} values for all electrocatalysts converge at -1.0 V vs RHE, larger differences are observed at lower potentials, especially at -0.6 V vs RHE, where CuO (A) exhibits a significantly higher resistance compared to CuO (B). CuO (R), on the other hand, shows intermediate behaviour.

Fig. 3. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of a) CuO (A) and b) CuO (B) samples with nanoplate structure. Insets show HRTEM images providing the lattice fringe spacing.

Fig. 4. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis for a) CuO (R); b) CuO (A), and c) CuO (B), measured at different applied biases ranging from -0.2 to -1.0 V vs RHE. The inset shows the mathematical model used for EIS fitting.

Fig. 5. a) Charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) as a function of applied potential for the three different materials, measured over an applied bias range of -0.2 to -1.0 V vs RHE; b) Capacitance ($\mu F cm^{-2}$) and electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) of the different Cu-based electrocatalysts.

However, at lower potential, the R_{ct} for CuO (R) becomes higher. From -0.2 to -0.6 V, the trend between CuO (A) and CuO (B) remains consistent, but it reverses at -0.8 V. The non-linear profiles of R_{ct} with the applied potential indicate a change in the electrocatalytic behaviour, as discussed later.

The EIS data were further analysed to estimate the electrochemical active surface area (ECSA) of the samples using the capacitance method, consisting of cycling the electrodes at different scan rates in a non-faradaic charging process [46]. By plotting a graph of charging current vs. scan rate, the double layer capacitance value (C_{dl}), can be obtained by the slope of the curve, and then the ECSA can be calculated as follows:

$$ECSA[cm^2] = \frac{C_{dl} [\mu F]}{c [\frac{\mu F}{cm^2}]} \quad (3)$$

where c is the specific charge density. Details about calculations are reported in SI.

Fig. 5b summarises the results. The ECSA values range from 30 to 55 cm^2 , following a trend consistent with the observations in Fig. 5a at -0.6 V, although different from the behaviour at less negative potentials. Determining ECSA is crucial for electrocatalytic studies; however, few studies have examined this aspect, particularly for CuO electrocatalysts. Compared to similar electrocatalysts [46–48], our CuO samples exhibit significantly higher ECSA values, confirming the successful synthesis of highly electrochemically active CuO samples via the

hydrothermal method.

Further insights into the behaviour of the three materials were obtained through chrono voltammetry tests, as summarised in Fig. 6a. Although the overall shape of the curves remains unchanged, given that all catalysts are based on CuO, differences emerge in the onset potentials for H₂ evolution at potentials below -0.6 V. This onset potential shifts to less negative values in the order Cu (R) \rightarrow Cu (A) \rightarrow Cu (B) (see the current density at a fixed potential, e.g. at -0.8 V). However, near the onset potential (-0.6 V) the order changes, as evidenced by the magnification of the plot shown in Fig. 6b, following the capacitance and ECSA trends shown in Fig. 5b. These results are consistent with the changes in the R_{ct} order observed between -0.6 and -0.8 V in Fig. 5a.

As H₂ evolution begins to dominate the current density at potentials more negative than -0.8 V, where diffusion phenomena no longer control the electrochemical process, the morphology of the CuO nanoparticles (from round shaped as in Cu (R) to nanosheets of varying lengths in CuO (B) and CuO (A) samples) plays a crucial role in determining reactivity (i.e., current density). These results indicate that around this potential, a transition occurs between regimes controlling the process, shifting to one where the availability of protons for H₂ evolution governs the behaviour. Consequently, a change in selectivity and product distribution between C₁ and C₂₊ products (e.g., CO₂RR products with two or more carbon atoms) is expected.

Fig. 6. a) Chrono voltammetry profiles from 0.4 to -1.2 V vs RHE for the different electrocatalysts, conducted under a CO₂ stream; b) Enlarged view of the region between -0.5 and -0.9 V.

3.3. CO₂RR behaviour

The CO₂RR behaviour was investigated in a flow-type compact device to obtain reliable data on performance under relevant conditions, addressing the limitations of many studies employing H-type or similar electrocatalytic reactors, as discussed elsewhere [29]. The potential range explored was from zero to -1.0 V, covering regions both below and above the changes in behaviour observed in the previous experiments. The current profile, normalised to the ECSA for consistency, is shown in Fig. 7a. A clear shift towards more negative potentials is observed in the exponential increase of current density across the three samples, following the activity order: CuO (A) \rightarrow Cu (B) \rightarrow CuO (R). This trend differs from that observed in chrono voltammetry profiles (Fig. 6a). This discrepancy derives from the differing experimental conditions, i.e. scanning potential during chrono voltammetry analysis versus continuous operation in these electrocatalytic tests (Fig. 7a). Notably, below the threshold for the exponential rise in current density, the reactivity order changes, as also observed in chrono voltammetry data. However, the error margin in this region is higher due to the low current density values.

Above the threshold for the exponential increase in current density, there is a rapid increase in the side H₂ formation, as well as in the products of CO₂RR. The total carbon Faradaic Efficiency (FE), i.e. the Faradaic selectivity for CO₂RR versus HER, increases, reaching a near plateau at a normalised current density of about 0.2 – 0.3 mA cm⁻². Notably, there are significant differences in total carbon FE among the three catalysts, with CuO (A) exhibiting over 50 %, CuO (B) around 20 %, and CuO (R) approximately 25 % (Fig. 7b). These findings highlight considerable intrinsic differences in CO₂RR vs. HER among these CuO electrocatalysts.

The product selectivity, including C₁ versus C₂₊ formation, where C₁ represents single-carbon products and C₂₊ refers to multi-carbon products, also varies significantly and depends on the applied potential. Fig. 8 presents the total carbon FE for C₁ (Fig. 8a) and C₂₊ products (Fig. 8b) as a function of the normalised current (to ECSA). The FE distribution of products as a function of the applied potential is instead shown in Fig. 9.

These results indicate a series of relevant observations. The first insight from Fig. 8 is that at low current densities, e.g. at potentials below the previously discussed threshold, the FE to C₂₊ products can reach up to 100 %. As the current density, potential, and availability of hydrogen increase, there is a complete switch to C₁ products, which also reach a total FE of up to 100 %. This result indicates that the selective formation of C₂₊ versus C₁ products strongly depends on the reaction conditions and availability of hydrogen (the latter limited at low current densities/potentials, as commented before), rather than on the intrinsic

properties of the catalyst itself. The role of the intrinsic electrocatalyst's characteristics is secondary. For example, the more intrinsically active CuO (A) (Fig. 7a) shows the switch from C₂₊ to C₁ at lower normalised current, around 30 μ A cm⁻² (and at a lower potential). In contrast, CuO (B) maintains a high C₂₊ selectivity up to approximately double this normalised current density, corresponding to a more negative applied potential (about -0.4 V vs. -0.2 V for CuO (A)).

This difference is significantly reflected in the product distribution and types formed during CO₂RR (Fig. 9). At zero potential versus RHE, the main products are acetic acid, oxalic acid, and ethanol. Contrary to common assumptions that high potentials are necessary for C₂ product formation, these results do not support this consideration, as C₂ products can form with total carbon FEs exceeding 90 % even at low current densities, with the remaining being formic acid (FA). While all CuO samples produce the same types of products, their relative distributions differ, with CuO (B) achieving an FE to ethanol above 50 %, compared to around 30 % for CuO (A) and CuO (R). These differences primarily arise from variations in oxalic acid production and minor differences in other products.

At more negative potentials, ethanol rapidly disappears. In contrast, oxalic acid (formed by dimerization of CO₂ anion radicals through a one-electron transfer to CO₂) increases in FE before declining at more negative potentials. CuO (B) and CuO (R) exhibit oxalic acid selectivities up to 90–95 %, while CuO (A) predominantly produces CO, with FEs up to 80 %. This observation aligns with the lower onset for current density versus the potential observed in CuO (A) (Fig. 7a), which results in more hydrogen availability for surface reduction reactions. Thus, CO₂ can be reduced to CO at a potential of -0.2 V in CuO (A), whereas in CuO (B) and CuO (R), CO₂ anion radicals are more abundant and dimerise to form oxalic acid. However, at more negative potentials, sufficient hydrogen becomes available on the surfaces of CuO (B) and CuO (R), and CO becomes the dominant product. FA, derived from the further hydrogenation of carboxylate species, remains a minor product compared to oxalic acid (at lower potentials) and CO (at higher potentials). The FA formation is thus not the primary CO₂RR pathway for these electrocatalysts.

A mechanistic understanding based on catalyst structure and composition, including factors such as Cu facets, the presence of defective sites, and oxygen atoms, cannot explain these results [10]. The electrocatalytic behaviour is primarily governed by the availability of enough surface hydrogen for CO₂RR rather than intrinsic differences in the nanostructure of CuO. The nanostructure mainly affects the availability of surface hydrogen due to changes in the hydrophobic properties of CuO. In previous work [49], it was demonstrated that altering the hydroxyl surface concentration (by annealing) shifted the properties of CuO from hydrophilic to hydrophobic. The different morphologies of the

Fig. 7. a) Current normalised (to ECSA) vs. applied potential and b) Total carbon Faradaic Efficiency (FE) vs. current normalised (to ECSA) for CuO electrocatalysts.

Fig. 8. Total carbon FE to C₁ products (a) and to C₂₊ products (b) versus the current normalised (to ECSA) during CO₂RR experiments on CuO electrocatalysts.

Fig. 9. FE to carbon products vs the potential applied in CO₂RR tests on a) CuO (A), b) CuO (B) and c) CuO (R) electrocatalysts.

CuO samples influence the concentration of hydroxyl groups (associated with surface defects), which in turn affects the hydrophilic character of CuO and the availability of hydrogen atoms for the reduction of chemisorbed CO₂ or CO₂ anion radicals formed by outer-shell one-electron transfer.

Although CuO (A) and CuO (B) show the same nanostructure, their electrocatalytic behaviour in CO₂RR differs significantly. This difference is attributed neither to structural or morphological factors, nor to distinct wettability properties. However, these aspects are only functional to have a series of homogeneous electrocatalysts allowing the correlation between the switch from C₂₊ to C₁ paths and proton accessibility to the surface, which depends on both the applied potential and the wettability characteristics of the electrocatalyst. As described, the two samples were synthesized using different precursors, i.e. Li⁺ for CuO (A) and Na⁺ for CuO (B), which led to differences in proton accessibility at the catalyst-electrolyte interface. These results indicate that factors other than the nature of surface-active sites in copper-based samples play a decisive role in determining CO₂RR performance and selectivity to C₁ and C₂₊ products. In other words, identical nanostructures can yield different CO₂RR selectivities if the surface proton accessibility is modulated, providing a new perspective on the design of CO₂RR catalysts.

3.4. Influence of hydrophobicity on CO₂RR reactivity

Recent studies have shown that adding a suitable functionalisation agent can alter the wettability properties of catalysts [33,50–52]. For example, Wang et al. [52] reported that incorporating stearic acid during the preparation of CuO/ZnO catalysts creates a hydrophobic layer on the surface, enhancing both catalytic performance and

selectivity in CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol. To investigate the effect of electrode wettability on CO₂RR reactivity, we functionalised a commercial CuO sample with stearic acid to induce a more hydrophobic character (see SEM-EDX images presented in Figures S3 and S4 in SI in comparison with a non-treated sample). In electrocatalytic reactions, increasing hydrophobicity can regulate proton access to the electrode surface through diffusion, thereby enhancing process selectivity.

The treated catalyst was deposited on a GDL following the same materials and methods used for the preparation of the other electrodes. Fig. 10 compares the stearic acid-treated CuO/GDL electrode with the CuO/GDL electrode not subjected to the hydrophobic treatment. Particularly, Fig. 10a shows two images of a water droplet on the electrode surface, evidencing a greater contact angle for the stearic acid-treated electrode (117.4° vs. 103.4°), indicating a significant increase in hydrophobicity. The different wettability of the electrode treated with stearic acid induces a significant shift in the onset potential, as shown by the cyclic voltammetry (CV) tests reported in Fig. 10b.

These tests confirm that the hydrophilic/hydrophobic properties of the electrode surface significantly influence CO₂RR reactivity by altering the transport phenomena of species in solution. This induced effect can outweigh the intrinsic properties of the catalyst itself, as demonstrated in this study, where the same type and morphology of the electrocatalyst (CuO prepared via hydrothermal treatment) were used across different treatments (Li- or Na-based precursors). In general, a more hydrophobic electrode surface shifts the onset potential to less negative values, thereby influencing CO₂RR reactivity, as demonstrated by the results reported in Fig. 9.

Figure S5 presents images of water droplets on the electrode surface for CuO (A), CuO (B), and Cu (R) electrodes. The highest contact angle was measured as 129.7° for CuO (R), followed by CuO (A) (110.9°). Due

Fig. 10. a) Pictures of a water droplet over the electrode surface for contact angle measurements and b) cyclic voltammetry (CV) analysis for CuO/GDL electrodes treated and untreated with stearic acid.

to its more hydrophilic nature, no contact angle measurement was possible for CuO (B). These results are consistent with the cyclic voltammetry analysis shown in Fig. 6.

An analysis of the number of functional groups favouring the access of protons towards the electrode surface was performed via titration (detailed procedure provided in SI). These measurements are directly related to the solution's conductivity in the proximity of the electrode surface. The higher pH increase was observed for CuO (B) ($\Delta\text{pH}=3.1$), followed by CuO (R) ($\Delta\text{pH}=2.3$) and CuO (A) ($\Delta\text{pH}=1.7$). These results show an inverse correlation with the charge transfer resistance (R_{CT}) and capacitance, as presented in Figures S6 and S7, respectively.

4. Conclusions

This study aims to clarify a central question in the CO₂ reduction reaction (CO₂RR) concerning the formation of multicarbon species: does the presence of only specific sites control the switch of selectivity from C₁ to C₂₊ products in CO₂RR? In other words, is the formation of C₂₊ products governed solely by specific active sites? To address this, we designed a set of targeted experiments. Investigating the structure-reactivity relationship or the role of wettability was not the main objective; rather, these aspects were functional in designing experiments that can effectively answer the question above.

From this perspective, the main result, which to our knowledge was never reported in the literature, is to evidence that it is possible a complete switch (nearly 100 %) in the selectivity to C₂₊ versus C₁ production as a function of the increasing applied potential. The potential at which the shift occurs is a function of the accessibility of protons to the catalyst surface, which is correlated to the wettability of the catalysts and also determines the normalised reaction rate. There are instead minor differences in the type of products formed and the relative Faradaic selectivity. We believe that these key results demonstrate that the path to C₂₊ versus C₁ products in CO₂RR is not an intrinsic property of the electrocatalyst but depends on the availability of surface protons, which is a function of the operating conditions and electrode characteristics.

In addition to the above aspects, this study also shows, as a secondary aspect, that the structural and electrochemical properties of CuO-based electrocatalysts, synthesised under hydrothermal conditions, significantly impact their performance in CO₂RR. The use of different alkaline precursors (LiOH, NaOH) alters the hydrophilic/hydrophobic balance, which in turn governs the availability of active sites for CO₂RR. CuO (A) and CuO (B) exhibited notable selectivity towards multi-carbon products, with CuO (A) being particularly efficient in producing C₂₊ multi-carbon products at lower applied potential but changing the carbon

selectivity at higher current densities. These findings suggest that the hydrophilic/hydrophobic properties and nanomorphology play critical roles in controlling both the reaction pathways and product distribution. When comparing CuO (A) and CuO (B) to CuO (R), a clear structural influence on CO₂RR performance emerges. The reference sample, in fact, shows a distinct morphology (aggregates of round nanoparticles) with non nanoplates observed. Notably, although the CuO (R) has similar wettability properties with respect to CuO (A) electrode, it shows lower DL capacitance and ECSA, which can be attributed to its different nanoarchitecture. However, although CuO (A) and CuO (B) show the same nanostructure, their electrocatalytic behaviour in CO₂RR differs significantly. This difference is attributed neither to structural or morphological factors, nor to distinct wettability properties. These aspects are only functional to have a series of homogeneous electrocatalysts allowing the correlation between the switch from C₁ to C₂₊ paths and proton accessibility to the surface, which depends on both the applied potential and the wettability characteristics of the electrocatalyst. Future work should focus on optimising these parameters to enhance the production of valuable C₂₊ products, offering a promising pathway for efficient CO₂ utilisation and conversion into sustainable fuels.

From a general mechanistic perspective, the possibility of switching the selective path from C₂₊ to C₁ products by increasing the surface availability of H (and with this transition being dependent on the wettability of the electrocatalyst) raises the question of whether the crucial issue to design electrocatalysts for ambitious targets, such as CO₂ to ethylene, depends (only) on realising specific active sites on the electrocatalyst. As remarked above, these tests were conducted with electrodes and cells relevant from a practical perspective, providing valuable indications on the effective aspects determining the behaviour for industrial electrocatalytic applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Gabriele Centi: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Claudio Ampelli:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Siglinde Perathoner:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Mario Samperi:** Investigation. **Chiara Genovese:** Methodology, Conceptualization. **Angela Mercedes Ronsisvalle:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Daniele Giusi:** Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcou.2025.103188](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2025.103188).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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